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YUFE TRANSFORMING R&I THROUGH EUROPE-WIDE
KNOWLEDGE TRANSFER

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D4.4 Strategy for a European Career Track System

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List of Abbreviations and Definitions

CoARA	Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment
DIOSI	Developing and Implementing hands-on training on Open Science and Open Innovation for Early Career Researchers Project
DORA	Declaration on Research Assessment
ERA	European Research Area
OTM-R	Open, Transparent and Merit-based Recruitment of Researchers
RESAVER	Retirement Savings Vehicle for European Research Institutions
“Researcher”	We understand a 'researcher' to be any student or member of staff with a research component in their workload. For the purpose of this report, we include doctoral candidates and academic staff with research duties in the term 'researcher'.
WP	Work Package
YUFE	Young Universities for the Future of Europe
YUFE CFR	YUFE Competence Framework for Researchers

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Strategy for a European Career Track System

1. Mapping of research career paths and researcher competency frameworks

1.1 Introduction

The Young Universities for the Future of Europe (YUFE) share the vision of a European Research Area with free circulation of researchers, scientific knowledge, and technology. Work is being completed within YUFE to develop common tools to enable professional development exchanges and upward career paths such as joint YUFE Career Tracks.

However, our academic YUFE partners all have different national systems featuring different national regulations towards research, careers, mobility, selection procedures for entry and advance in positions, and assessment criteria. To make the YUFE career paths aligned and to foster mobility, we needed a better understanding of the YUFE partners' national career systems and the national and local research training and research funding landscape. Therefore, this work package aimed to explore academic career systems in more detail to identify challenges and potential solutions to enhance researcher mobility and a YUFE Career Track.

The work on this task is structured in sub-tasks as follows:

1. Mapping of academic career paths in the eight YUFE universities (entry and exit points); hiring practices and official requirements of skills and qualifications; evidencing research development and teaching skills; as well as the range of selection criteria for academic positions and tenure in YUFE partner countries.
2. Mapping of all researcher competency frameworks already in place at our ten YUFE universities.
3. Establish recommendations at European, national, and institutional level to overcome the obstacles for talent circulation.
4. Advice to develop a Strategy for a European Career Track System, making references to the ERA Policy developments.

1.2 The Mapping Process

A questionnaire was devised to capture details from individual institutions in order to gather the relevant information on YUFE partners' varying career progress and procedures. It was agreed by the WP4 members to use the EURAXESS R1-R4

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research profile descriptors¹ as a common European framework for this task. The questionnaire asked for information in the following areas:

1. Academic career progression stages and job titles, aligned to R1-R4 research profile descriptors;
2. Training packages provided to support academic career progression and development (both mandatory and optional);
3. Recruitment process for academic positions;
4. Permanency and promotion procedures for academic positions (including if a tenure-track system is in place);
5. Any time limits that are imposed on holding academic positions;
6. Minimum professional and academic qualifications for each R1-R4 position;
7. Requirements and demonstrable metrics needed to move through the career levels (i.e., R1 to R2; R2 to R3; R3 to R4);
8. Increments for promotion to R4;
9. Requirements and demonstrable measures for promotion within R4;
10. Institutional networks or schemes to support academics working towards promotion;
11. Outline of the evaluation and performance review processes at each institution;
12. Outline of the process for promoting staff to leadership/management roles;
13. Any other notable challenges or obstacles to mobility and circulation of talent.

A copy of the questionnaire used can be found in Annex 1.

Partner institutions were also asked to provide copies of their own university's researcher competency framework so that these could be mapped and compared.

1.3 Methodology

According to the proposal, the first step in the deliverables of this work task was: *“Mapping of research career paths in the [ten]YUFE universities (entry and exit points), hiring practices and official requirements of skills and qualifications, evidencing research development and teaching skills, as well as the range of selection criteria for academic positions and tenure in YUFE partner countries”*.

To achieve this mapping, Dr Anney Lax (then task 4.1 leader from the University of Essex) and Charlotte Simmat (WP4 leader from the University of Bremen) created a questionnaire to be filled out by all YUFERING partners. The questionnaire was designed to begin the investigation of the research career paths in the YUFE universities (entry and exit points). The questions aimed to understand more about the range of selection criteria for academic positions and tenure in YUFE partner countries, in order to work towards creating the vision of a European Career Track and identifying obstacles and potential solutions for balanced mobility. The questions focussed on different aspects:

- research career paths in the [ten] YUFE universities (entry and exit points);

¹ [EURAXESS Research profile descriptors](#)

- hiring practices and official requirements with regards to skills and qualifications;
- evidence of research development and teaching skills;
- the range of selection criteria for academic positions and tenure in YUFE partner countries.

First, a draft version of the questionnaire template was presented to the WP4 group members for feedback, which was collected and included in the final questionnaire. This final version of the questionnaire was sent to all WP4 members in July 2021. Each WP4 member was encouraged to consult the colleagues at their institution who could help answer the questions. It was explained to the colleagues completing the questionnaire that the answers did not need be too lengthy or exhaustive, and that they were free to insert diagrams or charts, for clarity. It was also acknowledged that not all questions would be relevant to all institutions, and knowing the differences in practices or lack thereof would also be important.

2. Findings

2.1 Summary of findings

The findings from the data collection exercise were then summarised into four distinct areas:

1) <u>Entry and Exit Points</u>	
Commonalities	Differences
Transition from R1 to R2 is focused on independent work and research	Additional work available at post-doc level In some countries there is a habilitation process to transition between doctoral work and professional academic work
Doctoral candidates are considerate non-permanent staff	In some countries doctoral candidates are considered students
All partners have different academic career levels	The different career levels (R1-4) don't correspond exactly to the same criteria across partners
All partners provide doctoral training	Students in the UK are not eligible for staff training

2) <u>Hiring practices and official requirements of skills and qualifications</u>	
Commonalities	Differences
Criteria for recruitment and promotion in place at institutions	Different requirements across levels and appointment type

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All provide both permanent and fixed-term appointments	The criteria for contract types and length are different, and related to legal and/or national requirements
Mixture of teaching and/or research responsibilities and workload in academic contracts	In some countries this depends on individual appointments, roles and negotiations; in other countries this is mandated centrally
Recruitment is open externally to all candidates who meet the criteria	In the UK, the recruitment and advertising model follows a common private organisation model; in other countries recruitment is done at a national level with a competition
	In some countries, academic posts are considered public/civil servants, rather than institutional appointments, and are only open to citizens
	Requirements around qualifications, length of service, metrics and performance vary across countries
	In some institutions Principal Investigators on grants have freedom to adopt their own hiring practices

3) Research development and teaching skills

Commonalities	Differences
Optional training provided in a range of skills	Varying requirements across institutions regarding mandatory training
	Difference in who provides training – centralised, outsourced, or at faculty/department level
	Content of training provided varies – teaching skills, professional skills, research/project based and funding

4) The nature of academic posts and tenure.

Commonalities	Differences
Open public recruitment competitions for R1- R4 posts that include both teaching and research	Time constraints regarding access to different career levels (Germany, Croatia)

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All professorial appointments require significant previous experience in academic roles	In some countries promotions at all levels are dictated by criteria; in other countries a move to a higher grade is based on time of service. In others both these issues are considered
	Tenure track schemes used in some countries

2.2 Exploration of similarities and differences across partners

2.2.1 Entry and Exit Points

The data collection exercise in this area highlighted that some similarities exist between partners – for example with all institutions providing doctoral training as standard and acknowledging doctoral candidates as non-permanent staff (when considered as staff rather than students). Partners were also common in their approach to the transition process from R1 (first stage researcher) to R2 (recognised researcher) with focus being put upon the ability to carry out independent work and research to move up the scale. However, differences were also discovered, with all partners having different career levels which do not necessarily correspond to the same criteria across the R1 to R4 classifications. Additionally, in the British system doctoral candidates are considered as students (unless provided with a contract to work as research assistants or assistant lecturers), and therefore not considered eligible for training designed for and delivered to staff members. Differences were also noted regarding 1) the availability of a system of habilitation (which requires recognition of expertise and professional practice at a certain level for academics before they are able to apply for positions); and 2) the provision of additional work at post-doctoral level.

2.2.2 Hiring practices and official requirements of skills and qualifications

This area highlighted the most differences between partners across the alliance. Hiring practices across partners often depend on whether the candidate is hired for short-term posts (usually an externally funded position) whereby the university would typically have more flexibility, versus permanent positions where the hiring regulations may be stricter. In some countries, permanent posts are also likely to involve teaching and more legislation/civil service status. Some similarities are present in that, for example, all partner institutions have criteria that must be applied when recruiting and promoting staff, and most contracts have a combination of teaching and research responsibilities detailed for academic staff. Other parallels exist with staff positions being offered as both permanent and /or fixed-term appointments, and that recruitment is open to candidates both internally and externally who meet the selection criteria and person specification.

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However, differences in approach in this section highlighted that partner institutions have different requirements across staff levels and appointment type. The criteria required for various contract types differed, as well as the lengths of contracts available. In some countries, these are often related to legal and national requirements that cannot or can only partly be amended at the institutional level. In some contexts, the distribution of teaching and research allocation within workloads is dependent on a specific job role and could be negotiated. In other partner countries this split between tasks and time is mandated centrally at either a national or regional level and is non-negotiable. In the UK, the data collection found that the recruitment and advertising model used a common private organisation approach, whereas in some European partners recruitment was undertaken at a national level with a competition (dependent or not on achieving previous habilitation). Similarly, in some countries in Europe academic posts are considered as public, civil servant positions rather than institutional appointments, and as such are only open to citizens of that country. This area also showed differences surrounding qualification criteria, length of service, metrics used as evidence of progression/promotion and performance in hiring practices across countries. Finally, it was also noted that in some institutions, in particular, Principal Investigators on grants have complete freedom with regards to employment practices and are not restricted to abiding by any institutional processes and policies. This can then result in considerable differences regarding hiring practices within the same institution.

2.2.3 Research development and teaching skills training

In terms of career and skills development, all partners provide some level of training, whether essential and/or optional, with courses and sessions covering a range of skills for staff. However, the provision of skills varies across institutions in terms of the requirements for mandatory/optional training, and which body provides the training. At some institutions training is provided centrally, whereas at others it is delivered at faculty or department level or outsourced to an external provider. The content of training provision also varies across different areas with a focus on varying topics such as teaching skills, professional skills, research or project skills, and funding.

2.2.4 The nature of academic posts and tenure

For this area the data collection comparison highlighted that across partner institutions there is an open, public recruitment for posts across the R1 to R4 classifications that include both teaching and research within their remit. For professorial appointments, significant previous experience in academic roles is required to be appointed across all institutions. However, the parameters and interpretation of what a professorial role entails differ, as well as the number of years in their career, number and quality of publications, the measures of publication quality, the requirements of external grant funding, the need for other metrics (e.g., citation indexes, invited keynotes etc.). In most cases, these requirements are set at the national level and therefore cannot be amended to accommodate a 'one European university' model. For example, in Germany there are time constraints applied to the length of time an academic can

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spend at a particular career level before being excluded from progressing further. In some countries, promotions at all levels are dictated by application processes informed by criteria, whereas in other nations a move up to a higher grade is automatic based on an individual's length of service. The data collected also included tenure track schemes, which were only used at some partner institutions. Once again, the lack of consistency across educational contexts and the imposition of legal national requirements for appointments and career progression, make it impossible to design one single career track.

2.3 Discussion amongst partners

The similarities and differences across partner institutions' own local and national arrangements in all four areas were discussed at a focus group in November 2022. Partners were asked to consider the obstacles for talent circulation given the differences between the varying systems in each country, and whether these could be overcome. As part of the discussion, the group noted that although differences in some areas had been highlighted, where these were minor, it was not necessarily an obstacle for talent circulation. For example, if institutions have a different understanding or definition of the various career levels this does not necessarily have to be problematic providing the career levels/definitions used are clear and transparent to anyone wishing to move between institutions, and that there are explicit and fair equivalences. However, some of the differences at the system level posed challenges that seemed unsurmountable.

It was also noted that mobility was negatively impacted by the lack of visibility of academic vacancies across partners and the taken-for-granted local requirements and regulations, which were sometimes difficult to navigate, especially in countries where there is only one national open competition to fill vacant positions. The use of the EURAXESS – Researchers in motion website² was highlighted as a good tool as this lists job offers and funding opportunities across Europe and the world. Other initiatives that are now in place include the Human Resources Strategy for Researchers (HRS4R)³ which sets out guiding principles in a Charter & Code that research institutions can align their human resource policies to and achieve a “HR Excellence in Research” award. An ERA Talent Platform⁴ is also being set up to act as a single point of contact for researchers in Europe to manage their career development. Institutions can also make use of the OTM-R principles⁵ set out to promote equal opportunities and access to job vacancies.

The use of fixed term positions versus permanent appointments was also discussed and how this can impact on the stability of job roles and the attractiveness of vacancies. The group concluded that the next step would be to discuss amongst partners how to

² [EURAXESS | \(europa.eu\)](https://euraxess.eu)

³ [HRS4R | EURAXESS \(europa.eu\)](https://euraxess.eu)

⁴ [ERA Talent Platform \(europa.eu\)](https://euraxess.eu)

⁵ [Microsoft Word - OTM-R-finaldoc.docx \(europa.eu\)](#)

take the data and develop these into recommendations for overcoming the obstacles for talent circulation.

The group agreed that institutions should focus on developing their academics' skills, and in doing this create a stronger emphasis on transferable skills (rather than contextual ones only) to enable staff mobility across institutions and countries. This is even more important given that most doctoral students, once graduated, will go onto a career outside of academia. Even those that do engage in an academic career path may not stay in their original academic field as research is becoming more interdisciplinary. It is therefore important for researchers to be able to develop and articulate their transferable skills for use in the job market.

3. Recommendations at European, national and institutional level to overcome the obstacles for talent circulation

In January 2023 representatives from partner institutions met to develop potential recommendations to overcome the obstacles for talent circulation following the data collection and mapping exercises, and relevant discussions. A list of recommendations was subsequently drawn up and put out for consultation to all partners between March and May 2023. Following the consultation period, a list of recommendations was again discussed and refined in a group meeting (May 2023) with a final document agreed on by all. The agreed list of recommendations is presented below.

3.1 Recommendations at the institutional level

3.1.1 Entry and Exit Points

1. Institutional job bands and grading systems of positions to be mapped for equivalence against common bands (i.e., R1-4) of career progression, along with related key skills/experience.
2. Clear and explicit criteria to be published regarding national and institutional recruitments, and selection criteria, for all partners – for example around time constraints; degree requirements; nationality/language requirements (especially related to teaching obligations) etc.

3.1.2 Research Development and Training

1. Different types of training to be offered to all doctoral researchers, also drawing from other YUFE/DIOSI/YUFERING level initiatives (e.g., DIOSI 'train the trainer' sessions; WP4 supervisor training; soft skills; technical or research skills; employability skills, etc.).
2. Training and development to be embedded as a fundamental part of an academic's development, to include also support from supervisors (the latter at least in terms of information and or/knowledge sharing; the provision of personalised support; the signposting of support provided elsewhere).

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3.1.3 Hiring practices and official requirements of skills and qualifications

1. All institutions to continue to have and disseminate clear criteria for recruitment and selection at all career levels.
2. Provide guidance on contextual expectations for different job types (research; research and teaching; teaching only; management/leadership positions) and contract types (part/full time; continuous employment of short-term contracts; tenure track) around the different legal or institutional requirements in different institutional or national contexts. In particular:
 - a. In mapping career levels, experience and competencies, to consider requirements for skills/qualifications with clear recognition of previous salary and experience in each career level/band (i.e., R1-R4), even when previous roles were held in different countries.
 - b. Provide clear information regarding time constraints in terms of access, probation, different career levels, promotions, types of position and contract.
3. Institutions to keep candidates updated regularly throughout the application lifecycle regarding the status of their application.
4. Institutions to commit to implement OTM-R principles in their hiring practices.

3.1.4 Selection criteria for academic posts and tenure

1. Map terminology regarding job types and career levels to enhance clarity.
2. Criteria for recruitment and selection to be open to performance indicators that are not exclusive to one institution or national context.
3. Provide clear information around time limits and constraints that may apply to certain posts – access to different levels, types of position (permanent/probation), career levels.
4. Enhance inclusivity of selection criteria – for example by providing training for hiring committees; ensuring DORA recommendations are followed; following EDI (Equity, Diversity and Inclusion) guidelines.
5. Institutions to commit to implement OTM-R principles when selecting candidates.
6. Take into account progress within CoARA and similar EC driven initiatives and the contributions of the YUFE involved partner institutions in such frameworks.

3.2 Recommendations at the national level

1. Clear equivalences to be established with regards to acknowledging both academic performance and work/job aspects (e.g., roles, salary, seniority, membership of RESAVER pension fund) of the roles held in different countries.
2. Mapping carried out for each country of when national requirements may be negotiable, or when these are unsurmountable differences that may hinder mobility.

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3.3 Recommendations at the international level

1. Adopt the YUFE Competence Framework for Researchers (CFR) as standard to provide a YUFE-wide basis for academic staff development, staff selection and promotion, and individual career planning.
2. Continue to test and update our YUFE CFR in line with developments at European and/or national/regional levels, to align frameworks and practice wherever possible and relevant.

4. Strategy for a European Career Track System

This work package area of work aligns with the ERA Policy Agenda for 2022-2024⁶, especially with the ERA actions 4 and 5:

- 4) Promote attractive research careers, talent circulation and mobility.
- 5) Promote gender equality and foster inclusiveness.

The data collection and consultations stemming from this area of activity have highlighted the complexities surrounding the different legal, national and international requirements that are difficult to navigate amongst partners and affect academic mobility. This work package has identified areas where talent circulation is hindered, and has drafted the recommendations above to help overcome, or mitigate, the obstacles currently in place. It is proposed therefore that these recommendations (together with other work already being undertaken as part of the YUFE alliance – see appendices) should form an area of prioritisation and the foundation of any future strategy for an European Academic Career Track System.⁷

5. Conclusions

The work undertaken in this work package has mapped the academic/researcher career paths and researcher competency frameworks across ten YUFE partner institutions (see Appendix 4). This exercise highlighted the similarities and differences that currently exist within the alliance in the areas of researcher entry and exit points, hiring practices and official requirements of skills and qualifications, research

⁶ European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation: *European Research Area Policy Agenda – Overview of actions for the period 2022-2024* (https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/document/download/0c2f5f95-3274-4ab8-9acb-d6673dc238b8_en?filename=ec_rtd_era-policy-agenda-2021.pdf)

⁷ While a typical career track may include postdoctoral studies, different academic levels of progression (e.g., postdoctoral appointments, assistant professor, associate professor, full professor, emeritus professor), academic careers are not linear and it is not possible to establish a typical academic career route, both across and within academic systems.

development and teaching skills, as well as the range of selection criteria for academic positions and tenure in YUFE partner countries.

Using the information obtained by the mapping exercise it was then possible to draft recommendations at the institutional, national and EU level with a view to identify and mitigate the obstacles that currently hinder talent circulation. These recommendations can now be taken forward with other YUFE policies regarding staff recruitment and development to form the basis, together with HRS4R and the more recent EC promoted work on research and higher education frameworks of a European Academic Career Track System.

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6. Appendices

Appendix 1 Questionnaire template

<i>*if there are diagrams or charts that illustrate progression, please enclose</i>	
The outline steps of academic career progression at the institution – detailing the ladder of job titles and aligning against R1-R4 if possible	
Research & Teaching	
Teaching only	
Research only	
The programmes or training packages provided by the institution to support academic career progression and development	
Mandatory	
Optional	
Outline of the recruitment process for academic positions R1-R4 – indicating where there might be open, internal or restricted recruitment	
The permanency, and promotion procedure for academic positions – including if institution operates a tenure-track system for lecturers or professors	
Any time limits imposed on holding academic positions – not including roles recruited for time-bound research projects	
Minimum professional or academic qualification(s)	
For R1	

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For R2	
For R3	
For R4	
The requirements and demonstrable measures for R1 to move to R2	
Research	
Teaching	
Citizenship/ leadership/ career development	
Funding/Grant capture	
Public engagement/ creating societal impact/partnerships	
Professional practice/ esteem markers	
Internationalization/ Mobility/Languages	
Other	
The requirements and demonstrable measures for R2 to move to R3	
Research	
Teaching	
Citizenship/ leadership/ career development	
Funding/Grant capture	
Public engagement/ creating societal impact/partnerships	
Professional practice/ esteem markers	
Internationalization/ Mobility/Languages	
Other	
The requirements and demonstrable measures for R3 to move to R4	

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Research	
Teaching	
Citizenship/ leadership/ career development	
Funding/Grant capture	
Public engagement/ creating societal impact/partnerships	
Professional practice/ esteem markers	
Internationalization/ Mobility/Languages	
Other	
The increments of promotion for R4 at your institution – if applicable, please outline any definable gradations in the R4 category	
The requirements and demonstrable measures for promotion within R4	
Research	
Teaching	
Citizenship/ leadership/ career development	
Funding/Grant capture	
Public engagement/ creating societal impact/partnerships	
Professional practice/ esteem markers	
Internationalization/ Mobility/Languages	
Other	
Any institutional networks or schemes to support academics working towards promotion	
Outline of the evaluation and performance review process at the institution	

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Outline the process for promoting academic staff to management roles
Any other notable challenges or obstacles to mobility & circulation of talent

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Appendix 2 YUFE Competence Framework

The YUFE Competence Framework for Researchers is inspired by existing frameworks at some YUFE universities, and the European Competence Framework for Researchers (ResearchComp)⁸.

The YUFE Framework consists of 17 competences in four competence areas. Each competence is supported by a set of descriptors outlining its primary aspects. The competence areas are:

- Research
- Learning and Teaching
- Networking and Team Working
- Profile and Career Development
-

Competence area: Research

Competence	Descriptor
Research skills and techniques	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ability to recognise, validate and solve problems creatively, relating them to a wider context in nature or society. - Ability to apply original, independent, and critical thinking and to formulate new theoretical concepts. - Knowledge of most important and recent advances within one's field and in an interdisciplinary setting. - Understanding of relevant research methodologies and techniques and their appropriate application within one's research field and in an interdisciplinary setting. - Ability to critically analyse and evaluate one's findings and those of others and engage in peer reviewing. - Ability to summarise, document, report, disseminate and reflect on research progress.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Awareness and knowledge of sex and gender as a research topic, and, where relevant, integration of the sex and gender dimension into research & innovation content.
Research Management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ability to acquire and manage research projects, including team leadership, reporting and the use of funds. - Knowledge of how to acquire resources (national & EU funding). - Use of appropriate research infrastructure and resources.

⁸ European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Knowledge ecosystem: defining a European competence framework for R&I talents, Publications Office of the European Union, 2022, ([link](#))

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Research Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Contribute to addressing and solving complex problems in environment, society and science. - Contribute to advance the knowledge in one's research field and have an impact on the scientific community. - Science Outreach and Communication: Ability to communicate scientific findings both to professional and non-scientific audience. - Promote Flipped Knowledge Transfer⁹, meaning: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Ability to translate/ transfer research results, knowledge and expertise to society, and likewise get input from society. o Involve societal & business actors, citizens, NGO's and government in the research process as providers of input and co-creation partners. o Ability to manage Intellectual Property Rights (IPR). - Awareness and knowledge of community-engaged research and innovation principles¹⁰ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Actively involve affected community partners (non- academic communities) in one or more phases of the research and innovation process in a way that is mutually beneficial. o Encourage the implementation of the research outcomes and innovative solutions in partnership with the relevant communities. o Build trust-based relationships between researchers and community partners that take into consideration all partners' perspectives in defining research foci and innovation strategies
Open Science and Data Management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ability to recognise and apply open science principles in the related areas (Open Data, Open Publishing, Open Peer Review, Citizen Science, Open Source Software (OSS), Open Educational Recourses (OER)). - Knowledge and use of institutional, national and international repositories while applying FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) data principles and appropriate CC licencing. - Ability to manage research data and design Data Management Plans.
Professional Research Practice	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ethics and research integrity: Adhere to the recognised ethical practices and principles of research.

⁹ YUFERING Task 3.2: Concept-note on the “Flipped Knowledge Transfer Approach”, approved July 7th 2021

¹⁰ YUFERING Task 2.1: Community-engaged R&I (CERI) framework an definition, November 2021

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Understanding and awareness of different research contexts in different countries. - Understanding of relevant health and safety issues and demonstration of responsible working practices.
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Competence area: Learning and Teaching

Competence	Descriptor
Academic teaching	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ability to define teaching/course curricula and respective teaching execution plans. - Ability to teach in the subject area in which one is researching and in neighbouring areas. - Engagement in supervision and mentorship including the subsequent skills development. - Readiness to adapt to different teaching target audiences. - Knowledge of principles of pedagogy in higher education (application of various learning and teaching strategies, design of learning environments and design of assessment structures according to the principles of constructive alignment). - Methodological competences: student-centred learning and teaching (inquiry-based learning, cooperative learning, problem-based learning).
Gender, Diversity and Inclusivity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reflecting and taking into account gender, diversity and inclusivity in learning and teaching. - Knowledge of the guidelines and standards for designing an inclusive learning environment (e.g. accessibility for students with disability) - Using teaching methods that reflect gender and diversity aspects. - Including aspects of gender and diversity in the teaching content.
Innovation of teaching	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Willingness and ability to apply new learning and teaching methods - Participating in the further development of study programmes. - Being familiar with current digital/ blended learning and teaching tools (application of appropriate digital tools in L&T), including participation in/ production of MOOCs

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Competence area: Networking and Team Working

Competence	Descriptor
Teamwork	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ability to work in diverse teams (international, intercultural, and interdisciplinary). - Ability to work in an English-speaking team. If another language than English is the common language in the research field, ability to communicate in that language. - Awareness of unconscious bias as well as gender equality issues and awareness of the need to address its effects.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ability to listen, give and receive feedback based on critical and argument-based interaction.
Leadership	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Create and lead diverse teams, while considering aspects of gender and diversity. - Mentor individuals. - Recognise diverse talent and support individual development and career progression. - Negotiate and resolve conflicts.
Network	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develop networks within a discipline, within the institution, and in the wider research community. - Foster exchange and open collaboration. - Develop (inter)national networks and interact professionally and personally with peers.
Service to the institution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Participation in internal university commissions or committees. - Involved in research and teaching quality processes.

Competence area: Profile and Career Development

Competence	Descriptor
Awareness, resilience, flexibility and the willingness to learn	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ability to operate in a globalised world and deal with uncertainty and sudden changes to the working environment via a high degree of awareness, resilience, flexibility and the willingness to take learning opportunities. - International careers: Willingness to learn languages that facilitate working in a specific country, and willingness to adapt to the local context and local working processes.

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Career planning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The ability to identify and reflect on own competences and interests. - Ability to transfer skills to different professional contexts. - Ability to develop diverse career goals and career paths. - Seeking opportunities and being flexible: demonstrate an insight into the transferable nature of research skills, to other working environments, and the range of career opportunities within and outside academia. - Identify one's own (life-long) training needs. - Take ownership for and manage one's career progression, set realistic and achievable career goals, and identify and develop ways to improve employability. - Present one's skills, personal attributes and experiences through effective CV's, applications and interviews.
Self-organisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ability to successfully apply time management (identify and prioritize tasks, work according to suitable schedules). - Ability to cope with pressure, changes and challenges.
Entrepreneurial and societal spirit	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ability to turn ideas into action. This includes creativity, innovation and risk taking, as well as the ability to plan and manage projects in order to achieve objectives.¹¹ - Develop cooperation with business or societal stakeholders. - Recognizing the potential of commercial exploitation of research. This includes an understanding of market needs, recognizing the potential for new products and novel applications of research, and assessing the feasibility.

Appendix 3 Links to YUFE policies and strategies

1. [YUFE4Postdocs project](#)
2. [YUFE staff programme](#)
3. [YUFE staff development policy](#)

¹¹ Communication from the Commission to the Council, the European Parliament, the European Economic and Social committee and the Committee of the Regions: Implementing the Community Lisbon Programme: Fostering entrepreneurial mindsets through education and learning; COM/2006/0033 final, 2006 ([link](#))

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Appendix 4 YUFE Staff Recruitment Policy

YUFE

Staff Recruitment Policy

1. Preamble

All YUFE universities **share the view that**

- ...the academic and professional service staff in the universities of the YUFE Alliance are the key enablers of the YUFE European University.
- ...inclusive, merit-based recruitment is key to the success of the YUFE partners and as such the alliance is fully committed to providing opportunities in a fair, evidence based and transparent way.
- ...we should aspire to attract and select candidates with potential to grow and develop with the alliance.
- ...the principles of Open Transparent Merit based Recruitment (OTM-R) need to be applied to facilitate correct recruitment procedures and outcomes.

2. Challenges and Goals

A changing society drives universities to adapt proactively and continuously. The universities of the YUFE Alliance identify the following **challenges they want to address:**

1. In the current decade, staff attraction and retention at YUFE universities is less predictable than before, both for tenured and temporary academics as well as for professional service staff.
2. Even if their current employment is not their final destination, the variety of YUFE staff career paths and opportunities requires an overall vision on recruitment to ensure we continue to attract motivated, skilled and diverse talent on all career levels to our universities.
3. Behavioural competencies, such as openness, social engagement, flexibility, inclusiveness, critical thinking, resilience and self-management are essential to turn the YUFE alliance into a success and should be assessed alongside technical ability when recruiting.
4. Developing a European University requires an increasingly mobile and diverse workforce with strong language skills. Given the high ambition of YUFE to create a European University, the competence profile of all staff needed has become more comprehensive. Progressive, open and inclusive recruitment policies can help to address this.

Goals

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1. Creating inclusive, fair, open, and transparent appointment procedures based on the principles of the European OTM-R standards, welcoming applications from diverse backgrounds.
2. Becoming an attractive place for people in all career tracks (academic and professional service staff) and all career levels who want to drive the European University vision forward.
3. Recruiting all staff based on their knowledge, skills, potential and talents and empower all staff to build the YUFE university (young, student centred, non-elitist, open, inclusive).
4. Implementing the European Charter and Code and maintaining HR Excellence in Research Award status.
3. By adopting a joint staff recruitment policy, the universities of the YUFE Alliance **commit themselves** to
 1. ...advertising vacancies externally for academic and professional service staff, whenever possible.
 2. ...ensuring all advertised vacancies have clear job definitions, profile of the position and selection criteria.
 3. ...utilizing a wide range of advertising mediums, across multiple platforms (including the YUFE website) to attract a global workforce.
 4. ...shortlisting based only on how applicants demonstrate meeting the advertised criteria.
 5. ...ensuring interviews and other selection tools focus on establishing the applicants' ability to meet the advertised requirements of the job.
 6. ...ensuring members of interview and selection panels have been suitably trained, including in the objectives set out in the YUFE Diversity and Inclusivity Strategy (<https://yufe.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/04/YUFE-Diversity-and-Inclusivity-Strategy.pdf>)
 7. ...ensuring panel composition is gender balanced and represents diverse backgrounds.
 8. ...considering external panel members and including the student experience in academic recruitment where appropriate.
 9. ...providing feedback to all candidates on request.

The University Level: YUFE Member Universities' Staff Recruitment Policies

1. All YUFE universities subscribe to the YUFE staff recruitment policy.
2. Every YUFE university is strongly committed to the EU's Charter and Code as a fundament. Every YUFE university aims to acquire and maintain the HR Excellence in Research Award.

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3. Every YUFE university develops and applies consistently fair and equal HR policies that aim to promote Open, Transparent and Merit Based recruitment.
4. Every YUFE university regularly reviews its recruitment processes.
5. The leadership of every YUFE member university explicitly subscribes to the YUFE Staff Recruitment Policy and creates the framework conditions that enable its implementation.

The YUFE Level: YUFE Staff Recruitment Goals and Institutionalised Cooperation

1. The YUFE Staff Recruitment Policy is intended to complement, not replace, frameworks and guidance already in existence at member institutions: different recruitment, selection and employment laws may apply across the partner countries. **Local and national selection and employment laws will prevail.**
2. It is recognized that member institutions will be at different stages in their progress towards achieving the aims within the YUFE Staff Recruitment Policy, and accordingly a supporting Action Plan will be developed to provide a roadmap to institutional change to support the realization of this policy.
3. The YUFE members regularly review/debate the implementation of this joint YUFE Staff Recruitment Policy, which provides added value to their own staff recruitment policies and supports the YUFE ambitions.
4. The YUFE members regularly exchange experiences in recruitment and exchange best practices, thereby creating an expert group on recruitment as a nucleus for institutionalized exchange.
5. The joint effort for implementing the YUFE staff recruitment policy will contribute to creating a YUFE identity.

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Appendix 5 EU research profiles model R1-4 at the YUFE universities

EU research profiles model R1-4 at the YUFE universities										
R4	EU research profiles	UBremen	UCY	UAntwerp	UC3M	UMaastricht	UEF	UNIRI*	NCU	UEssex
	Leading Researcher (Researchers leading their research area or field)	Lifetime professorship (incl. cooperation professorship)	Academic staff at the ranks of Associate Professor, Professor. Research Professor, Research Associate Professor (Research Academics are hired on a contract basis)	Contract research staff (leading researcher): Postdoc researchers in a leading role with main responsibility in education or research or management and valorisation Senior Academic Staff (professorships) professor, full professor (Belgium has for 4 levels in professorships, these two	Full professor (with or without a Chair) Chair	Permanent professorship s; Some fixed term professor positions; who have their own research group and are fully independent financially and scientifically. Their salary is paid by the university and additional to their own research they fulfil multiple management	Permanent professorship; Some fixed term professor positions; Professors of Practice (temporary); Leading Researchers (temporary)	Full professors (in the case of research institutes: scientific advisers) and full professors with tenure (in the case of research institutes: scientific advisers with tenure).	R4 in Poland is a professor nominated by the President of Poland or with well-recognized research performance. Can be employed within one of 3 groups (researcher, research-teaching, teaching). Fully independent with the highest basic level of salary which is mentioned in	Professor

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				<p>professor and full professor are the highest levels, we classify the other 2 levels as R3)</p>		<p>and educational tasks.</p>			<p>the ordinance to the law of higher education. Permanent position (in Poland only first 33 months influences temporary contract unless the funds is external from the ministry)</p>	
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R3	Established Researcher (Researchers who have developed a level of independence)	Temporary professorship: - Professors in the Tenure-Track process - Junior professors - Substitute professors (not tenured) Independent postdocs in the academic mid-level sector: - Senior Lecturers and Senior Researchers (tenured) - Lecturers (fixed-term contract and permanent position) - Academic staff assigned with independent tasks in teaching and research (normally	Academic staff at the ranks of Lecturer, Assistant Professor. Research Lecturer, Research Assistant Professor (Research Academics are hired on a contract basis)	Contract research staff: Postdoc researchers in a managerial role with main responsibility in education or research or management and valorisation Senior Academic Staff (professorship s: Tenure Track Assistant professor, Associate professor)	- Full professor - Visiting professor/visiting lecturer - Senior researcher (Doctors with access to contract according to Ley de la Ciencia española- Science Spanish Law)	Assistant and associate professors which are paid by the university who lead a research group and are involved in teaching and supervision of PhD students.	- Tenure Track: Assistant & Associate Professorships (temporary-> will be appointed as a professor if requirements are met after tenure track). Independent senior researchers. - Senior Lecturer/ researcher (fixed term or permanent) - University Lecturers (mainly permanent); Senior University Lecturers (based on excellent teaching merits; permanent) - Finnish Academy researchers	Assistant professors (in the case of research institutes: research associates) with proven research independence record and associate professors (in the case of research institutes: senior scientific associates).	R3 in Poland (University Professor or associate professor). Fully independent researcher with habilitation or without it but with recognized research performance. Can be employed within one of 3 groups (researcher, research-teaching, teaching). Permanent position (in Poland only first 33 months influences temporary contract unless the funds are	Reader, Senior Lecturer
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		permanent position) - Leaders of junior research groups (internally or externally funded)					(temporary positions) - Research leaders (temporary positions)		external from the ministry).	
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R2	Recognised Researcher (PhD holders or equivalent who are not yet fully independent)	Postdocs in the academic mid-level sector: - Lecturers and Researchers in the Tenure-Track process (not tenured from the start) - Academic staff in qualification positions receiving base funding - Academic staff in qualification positions or projects financed by third parties	Academic staff at the ranks of Lecturer, Assistant Professor. Research Lecturer, Research Assistant Professor (Research Academics are hired on a contract basis) Post-Doctoral Researchers (contract basis staff)	Contract research staff (BAP): Postdoc researchers in an expert role with main responsibility in education or research or research and valorisation management Academic Assistant Staff (AAP): doctoral assistant	Specific assistant Doctoral assistant Post-docs researchers of middle academic tier. - University Lecturers (PhD required) - Academic staff in qualification positions receiving base funding - Temporary academic researchers positions or projects financed by third parties	Senior postdocs who received their position based on temporary funding which are developing their own independent research group and are involved also in teaching.	Post-docs researchers of middle academic tier. - University Lecturers (PhD required) - Academic staff in qualification positions receiving base funding - Temporary academic researchers positions or projects financed by third parties	Postdoctoral researcher. Depending on the career development, some of the assistant professors (in the case of research institutes: research associates) in the first couple of years of their track also fit in this category.	Named in Poland as an adjunct. Person who holds a PhD. Salary comes dependently with the call for the position (external or national). Can be employed within one of 3 groups (researcher, research-teaching, teaching). R2 in Poland are not recognized as fully independent researchers. Post docs who are working to achieve habilitation. Permanent position (in Poland only)	Senior Research Officer, Senior Research fellow, Lecturer
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									<p>first 33 months influences temporary contract unless the funds is external from the ministry).</p>	
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R1	First Stage Researcher (Up to the point of PhD)	Doctoral candidates (irrespective of funding source and status)	Researchers - Special Scientists for Research, Research Assistants, Early-stage Post-Doctoral Researchers (contract basis staff)	Contract research staff (BAP): All researchers who don't have a PhD (yet), doctoral candidates employed at university funds or doctoral candidates employed by external funds Academic Assistant Staff (AAP): graduate teaching & research assistant, teaching assistant	Doctoral students, part of them employed at the universities (and/or institutes) as research and teaching assistants.	Early stage postdocs who receive their salary via grants and are managing a research project lead by their supervisors.	Early Stage researchers (appointed by the dean); temporary positions. Scholarship holders, external	Doctoral students, part of them employed at the universities (and/or research institutes) as research and teaching assistants.	Graduates, doctoral candidates (participants of doctoral school) in Poland named as assistant accordingly with the Law of higher education. position within employment structure for academic teachers who can be employed within one of 3 groups (researcher, research-teaching, teaching). Salary comes dependently with the call for the position (external, national). R1	Research Officer, Research Fellow, postdoc, research assistant
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										(assistants) are not independent academic teachers. Permanent position (in Poland only first 33 months influences temporary contract unless the funds is external from the ministry).
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								<p>* The criteria for the various positions in the Croatian scientific system are defined in the relevant national legislation and the respective bylaws (Act on Higher Education and Science, Rulebook on the Conditions of the National Council for Science, Higher Education and Technological Development for the Election to the Scientific Ranks, as well as Rulebook on the Necessary Conditions of the Conference of Croatian</p>		
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								Rectors for the Evaluation of the Teaching and Professional Work in the Election to the Scientific and Teaching Ranks).		
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